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Questionnaire to measure Educational Technologies Acceptance in Moroccan Public Universities

Fernando Martínez-Abad¹,
Alicia García-Holgado¹,
Francisco J. García-Peñalvo¹,
M^a José Rodríguez-Conde¹,

¹Research Group in InterAction and eLearning (GRIAL)
University of Salamanca
[fma, aliciagh, fgarcia, mjrconde]@usal.es

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1. Introduction

The project “Support to the Higher Education system in Morocco within the framework of a rapprochement with the European Higher Education Area” (*Appui au Système de l’Enseignement supérieur au Maroc dans le cadre d’un rapprochement avec l’Espace européen de l’Enseignement*), is an European Project whose general objective is accompanying, assisting and promoting the reform of the Moroccan higher education system within the framework of its strategic vision 2015-2030 and its approach to the European Higher Education Area in order to improve the employability of graduates and the governance of the university system. The project is organized into 6 components that involve different Spanish institutions.

In the development of Component 3 (Mission 3.), *Diversification des modalités d’enseignement (stratégie e-learning)*, it is important to know the perception and opinion of teachers from Moroccan public universities related to the state, use and prospection of educational technologies (García-Peñalvo, 2018; García-Peñalvo & Seoane-Pardo, 2015; Gros & García-Peñalvo, 2016) in their teaching activity. To achieve this objective, a questionnaire based on the extended (Huang, Teo, Sánchez-Prieto, García-Peñalvo, & Olmos-Migueláñez, 2019; Sánchez-Prieto, 2018; Sánchez-Prieto, Hernández-García, García-Peñalvo, Chaparro-Peláez, & Olmos-Migueláñez, 2019; Sánchez-Prieto, Olmos-Migueláñez, & García-Peñalvo, 2016a, 2016b, 2017; Venkatesh & Bala, 2008) TAM model has been designed (*Technology Acceptance Model*). Thus, an evaluation model is proposed in which, in addition to evaluating the 3 usual dimensions of the TAM models (perceived utility, perceived facility, behavioural intention), 7 external dimensions are included related to social influence (Subjective norm; Social image), the professional context (Voluntariness, relevance, results of use, external control of the tool) and the personal context (Anxiety).

Figura 1. Technology Acceptance Model for educational technologies used by teachers at university level

The data collected will allow the experts to have a quantitative measure of the current acceptance and intention of future use of educational technologies to promote changes in teaching methods. These quantitative data will be complemented with qualitative techniques. It would be necessary to obtain a minimum response of 50-60 questionnaires in each of the public universities to obtain reliable data.

2. Questionnaire

2.1. General information

Q001. University name.

Q002. Gender (Man; Woman).

Q003. Age.

Q004. Teaching experience (Years).

Q005. Academic discipline (Sciences, Health Sciences, Social Sciences, Humanities, Engineering and Architecture).

Q006. Academic rank.

Q007. Professional level.

2.2. Attitudes towards the use of educational technologies for virtual teaching

Q008. Indicate your degree of agreement with the following statement using the following scale: 1=Completely disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Somewhat disagree, 4=Neither agree not disagree, 5=Somewhat agree, 6=Agree, 7=Completely agree.

- **Q008_1.** In my job, usage of technologies for teaching is important
- **Q008_2.** In my job, usage of technologies for teaching is relevant
- **Q008_3.** The use of technologies for teaching is pertinent
- **Q008_4.** I use technologies in my teaching voluntarily
- **Q008_5.** My supervisors require me to use technologies for teaching
- **Q008_6.** Although it might be helpful, using technologies for teaching is certainly not compulsory in my University
- **Q008_7.** I have no difficulty telling others about the results of using technologies for teaching
- **Q008_8.** I believe I could communicate to my workmates the consequences of using technologies for teaching
- **Q008_9.** The results of using technologies for teaching are apparent to me
- **Q008_10.** I would have difficulty explaining my workmates why using technologies for teaching may or may not be beneficial
- **Q008_11.** University has control over using teaching technology that the University provides
- **Q008_12.** I have at my disposal the resources necessary to use technologies for teaching
- **Q008_13.** Given the resources, opportunities and knowledge it takes to use technologies for teaching, it would be easy for me to do it
- **Q008_14.** In my University, I cannot use the technologies for teaching that I would like
- **Q008_15.** People who influence my behaviour think that I should use technologies for teaching

- **Q008_16.** People who are important to me think that I should use technologies for teaching
- **Q008_17.** In general, my University supports the use of technologies for teaching
- **Q008_18.** My workmates think that teachers should use technologies in our teaching
- **Q008_19.** Teachers who use technology in their teaching have more prestige than those who do not
- **Q008_20.** Teachers who use technology in their teaching are considered more innovative than those who do not
- **Q008_21.** In my University, using teaching technology is a necessary indicator to promote
- **Q008_22.** I doubt about using technologies in my teaching for fear of making mistakes that I cannot solve
- **Q008_23.** In general, using technologies for teaching makes me feel uncomfortable
- **Q008_24.** I feel is difficult to use technologies for teaching
- **Q008_25.** Using technologies for teaching in my job increases my productivity
- **Q008_26.** Using technologies for teaching enhances my effectiveness in my job
- **Q008_27.** Using technologies for teaching improves my performance in my job
- **Q008_28.** I find teaching technology to be useful in my job
- **Q008_29.** Using technologies for teaching does not require a lot of my mental effort
- **Q008_30.** In my teaching I it finds easy to get technology to do what I want it to do
- **Q008_31.** Interacting with technologies in my teaching does not require a lot of my mental effort
- **Q008_32.** I find the use of technologies for teaching to be easy to use
- **Q008_33.** I plan to use technologies for teaching in the future
- **Q008_34.** Assuming I had access to teaching technology in the future, I predict that I would use it
- **Q008_35.** Assuming I had Access to teaching technology in the future, I intend to use it

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